

Building a living lab learning framework: Understanding the types, processes, levels and outcomes of learning in living labs

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Abstract

Learning is an integral part of living lab activities and outcomes. This research in progress paper aims to understand the learning aspects in the collaborative activities and innovative outputs of living labs by developing an analytical learning framework for living labs and applying it to the case study of KLIMAP living labs in the Netherlands. The research adopts a mix of approaches, including qualitative document analysis, interviews and participation in brainstorming and knowledge sessions. The study develops a working analytical living labs learning framework. The preliminary findings of the framework in the KLIMAP living lab show different types of knowledge on content, capacity and network are intentionally or incidentally produced at different levels (individual, team, community) of a living lab.

Key words

Co-creation, innovation, learning, knowledge types, knowledge-levels

Introduction

A living lab is an organized, real-life and user-centered approach to innovation (Schuurman et al., 2013). Each living lab is designed differently based on its context, prerequisite and resources. Therefore, the motive and aims of living labs, their positions, participating stakeholders, their disciplinary backgrounds, available resources such as people, money, medium and time, and the employed methodologies vary for different living labs. The idea that the successful innovation derives its understanding from existing and emerging user needs prompted the integration of a higher degree of user-centeredness in the living lab approach, thus introducing the dimension of co-creation to the concept (Eriksson et al., 2005). Consequently, many present-day living labs have evolved to implement co-creative processes in their design and activities. In living Labs, collaborations between multiple stakeholders from multiple disciplines accelerate the innovation process (Leminen et al., 2016; Nyström et al., 2014) as they contribute heterogeneous resources and knowledge resulting in innovations (Edwards-Schachter et al., 2012; Leminen & Westerlund, 2012). shows the major components of living lab design and its effects.

Figure 1. Major components of living lab design and effects

For successful innovation, a combination of different types of knowledge, capabilities, skills and resources is required (Fagerberg, 2004). Hence, in most contexts, innovation comprises a social component, such as learning (Kohlgrüber et al., 2021). However, for many years, living labs remained focused on innovation in the technological context, with only recent living labs integrating learning aspects (Schuurman et al., 2013). By opening the innovation process to all relevant stakeholders through co-creation and

collaboration, living labs incorporate learning and knowledge development as an integral part of their design, activities and outcomes, as shown in *Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.* However, most works on living labs do not highlight their learning mechanisms. Therefore, this paper aims to understand the learning components of living labs and thereby incorporate a learning framework to living lab framework in the light of the KLIMAP living lab located in the Netherlands.

Figure 2. Major components of living lab design, effects and role of learning

Co-creation, innovation and learning

Co-creation is a fusion between collaboration (co) and creation, where collaboration indicates ‘with’ different cross-sectoral stakeholders, and creation signifies a productive way of thinking, seeing, and doing arising from relational knowledge practice (Franklin, 2022). Thus, co-creation facilitates a much-needed cross-sectoral and socially inclusive understanding to address relevant problems (Payne et al., 2008). As a result, co-creators bring massive social and organizational learning that triggers transformation. Successful co-creation depends on core competencies such as knowledge and on interactive environment that leads to better learning, sharing and understanding of actors’ needs, thus increasing the trust and quality of shared knowledge (Payne et al., 2008). When the actors collectively learn about and from each other by surpassing individual barriers, they co-create. Hence, co-creation is highly linked to the learning process in the given network. Likewise, innovation implies adopting a new idea or behavior (Jiménez-Jiménez & Sanz-Valle, 2011). Innovation can be conceptualized as knowledge creation, and at the same time, the knowledge creation process is also a driver of innovation (O Riordan, 2013). The development and

dissemination of innovations increasingly focus on exchanging knowledge, learning, and cooperation between actors and organizations. Accordingly, living labs foster collaborative actions and learning between stakeholders to support integrated and appropriate technological and social innovations in local practice and governance processes (Edwards-Schachter et al., 2012), as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Co-creation- innovation-learning model for living labs

KLIMAP

KLIMAP (KLIMaatAdaptaie in de Praktijk) aims to design innovative climate-adaptive pathways for sustainable land and water management transition. With a consortium of 24 parties consisting of regional authorities, private companies, and research institutes, KLIMAP focuses on agriculture and nature area in the Dutch sandy soil region (KLIMAP, 2022). Sandy soil poses a particular challenge due to its permeable nature, making it vulnerable to the effects of climate change, such as extreme drought (Ladányi et al., 2021). In the living lab work package of KLIMAP, potential innovations related to diverse crop types, improving water retention and soil structure are explored and tested in over 25 pilot areas via technical and nature-based solutions, shown in Figure 4. The major output of KLIMAP is insights into possible climate adaptation measures and ways to implement them in these areas. The resulting outcome would be a change in traditional land and water management methods to adapt to the changing climate, thus initiating social transformation and influencing policies.

Figure 4. Dutch landscape (left), KLIMAP experimentation areas (right)

Methodology

The research follows a qualitative analysis approach using multiple methods. First, desk research was conducted to understand levels, processes and types of learning and transfer these understandings into the living lab learning framework. Next, the case study was researched via document analysis, participation in brainstorming and knowledge sessions, and interviews with KLIMAP stakeholders. Qualitative document analysis was conducted to capture the timeline of KLIMAP activities and their learning aspects. The analyzed document comprised the minutes of living lab meetings and knowledge sessions from the last two years. However, more living lab meetings, workshops and knowledge sessions are planned in future, the analysis of which will be adapted to the main analysis—similarly, brainstorming and knowledge sessions allowed for data triangulation.

Further, semi-structured interviews were conducted with the coordinators, project leaders, field-experiment experts, knowledge session facilitators and people in similar positions actively involved in KLIMAP. The study follows a wide-adopted method in qualitative research, i.e., the snowball sampling procedure (Goodman, 1961). The study

started with a small pool of known informants and asked them to recommend potential interviewees. Questions were divided per themes such as design, process and outcome-related queries and questions on knowledge development, capacity building and networks. So far, only 20% of the planned interview have been conducted.

Analytical framework

A working analytical living lab learning framework is drawn to highlight different learning types, levels, processes, and outcomes through the lens of social learning (informal incidental learning) and organizational learning (intentional transdisciplinary learning), as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5. Working analytical learning framework with living lab as enabling environment, based on Bhatt (2000) and Cooke and Gorman (2009).

expands the central part of the learning framework. As research progresses, it will incorporate different learning processes and outcomes from the analytical learning framework.

Living lab as enabling environment for engagement and learning	Level of Learning	Individual/ member level	Group/ Team level	Organizational/ Community level
	Type of Learning			
	Knowledge sharing & creation on content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Developing comprehensive understanding and sharing existing factual knowledge, conceptual knowledge, procedural knowledge, as well as metacognitive knowledge regarding the content of the living lab (Anderson and Krathwohl 2001) Peer-review to critique, revise and refine ideas (Bhatt 2000) Generating a <i>new knowledge</i> 		
	Capacity Development & Knowledge adoption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capable to adopt, apply and transfer available and new-produced knowledge and skills Create tools, skills, process and structures that allow for desired change at personal level, as a group, and at organization level (Potter and Brough 2004) Peer-review to critique, revise and refine skills (Bhatt 2000) <i>New actions</i> 		
	Network Building & knowledge distribution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Partnerships to further deepen or broaden the knowledge (living lab experimentation) <i>New coalition</i> in the network of similar kinds Knowledge reusability and replicability in another field (Bhatt 2000) applicable knowledge directly available to users Knowledge network 		

Figure 6. Expansion of the central part of the living lab learning framework, based on Anderson and Krathwohl (2001), Potter and Brough (2004)

Preliminary Findings

From the data collected from KLIMAP, the following preliminary findings were observed.

1. Knowledge creation & sharing on content:
 - a. The individual stakeholders in the KLIMAP living labs learn through learning community and observational learning. The stakeholders organize learning sessions, field-experiments and participate in online or offline group discussions in the learning community. Similarly, observational learning in the stakeholders occurs from observing presentations from other stakeholders with diverse knowledge backgrounds, listening to the group discussions, observing how to use certain tools, etc. With these kinds of shared knowledge, all individuals create their mind-maps and understanding of the subject.
 - b. KLIMAP has designed sub-groups to have frequent communication and share their insights. Cross-experimental learning is crucial in large projects such as KLIMAP with diverse field-experiments. Hence, establishing sub-groups allows learning from each other experiences.
 - c. Failures are a great way to learn. Some failures are bound to occur during experimentation and innovation. Thus, judgement-free space for making mistakes and learning from them is available for individuals, teams, or organizations.
2. Capacity development & knowledge adoption:
 - a. With all the field-experiments and research on upscaling, KLIMAP aims to create

a list of possible adaptation measures and ways to implement them in the study location. This tool can significantly benefit individuals or organizations (users) who will apply it in practice.

3. Network building & knowledge distribution:
 - a. KLIMAP supports open communication and collaboration among its stakeholders and similar external projects. As a result, various new coalition was formed during the living lab experimentation, e.g., new combination of knowledge on hydrology and agronomics in the study area.

Conclusion

The research, when completed, aims to highlight the importance of learning in the living lab, both as a process and product. It intends to develop a comprehensive learning framework to evaluate different types, levels, and processes of learning in living labs. Then, the outcome derived from such learning will be explored to capture the significance of learning in living labs. The result will offer valuable insights to researchers and practitioners in understanding the significance of living labs beyond their immediate results.

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